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Marketing of LIS Products and Services in Select Medical Libraries of Delhi in Digital Environment: A Comparative Study

Manika Lamba* and R.K.Bhatt**

* Research Scholar, Department of Library and Information Science, University of Delhi-110007
E-mail: lambamanika07@gmail.com

** Associate Professor, Department of Library and Information Science, University of Delhi-110007
E-mail: rakeshkumarbhatt@yahoo.co.in

Abstract- This article deals with the need of marketing of library products and services in medical libraries in the digital environment. It analyses the data collected from the two major medical libraries of India using GNU PSPP software and draw comparison among their marketing strategies.

Keywords - Marketing, Health Libraries, LIS products & services, Digital Marketing, National Medical Library of India (NLM), Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR).

1. Introduction

Medical science is considered as an integral part of a nation development and not merely a “subsystem” of the socioeconomic system. Being a signatory of Alma-Ata Declaration of 1978, the Parliament of India approved a National Health Policy in 1983. This policy indicates India’s commitment to the goal of development of the country in the field of medicine. The quality of medical research depends largely upon the exchange and communication of information. The medical literature should be easily accessible to the researchers, doctors and the practitioners, so that they can use it to its full advantage. Although, the literature is adequately indexed and abstracted yet the researchers and practitioners does not always make full use of it. It may be that they are unaware as how to use a medical library or never taken the trouble to learn how to use it. Thus, this is where the marketing of Library and Information Science (LIS) products and services steps in to address the problem of unawareness, improper utilization and to determine the degree of satisfaction by the user of the medical library resources.

1.1 Marketing by Medical Libraries

Rowley (2001) described marketing as a management process by which customer or user requirements are identified, anticipated and supplied efficiently and profitably. In the same vein, goods / products and services are offered in marketing and libraries to meet the needs of their target user groups. The process of marketing includes market research, identifying the consumer needs and demands, their pricing and promoting them to the appropriate consumers. The main purpose in marketing is attracting and retaining a growing base of satisfied customers. Libraries have become increasingly multi-disciplinary, collaborative and networked. With the advent of Internet the health professionals are able to generate, communicate and exchange information at a faster pace. In the face of this competition, library managers need to market their services to actual and potential users.

Marketing is one of the strategic tools of management. Marketing a library service has the objective of engaging people in a relationship, which will encourage them to use the service

and to continue doing so in the long term. It entails knowing or anticipating what users want, communicating to them what is available and being able to provide it to a level that is satisfactory to them. Decisions have to be made about which services to provide and whether they can be delivered effectively and efficiently within the resources available. The range of services on offer represents the library’s “marketing mix”. It is a balance of the 4 Ps – product, price, place and promotion. Some authors like to add additional ‘Ps’, such as people or process. The balance of these factors for each client group may be slightly different so the library may have to target its efforts towards different parts of its customer base at different times. Marketing a library is about the relationship between it and its actual and potential users. The latter have to know the library is there and be made aware of what it has to offer. They must use the service, support the financing of it and be willing to continue to do so over time. In view of the social, economic and technological changes, library and information centers have begun to realize that marketing of information products and services is an integral part of administration.

Nowadays, with the advancement in technology the resources have shifted from print to electronic and digital era. Digital information services which is described by Ravichandran and Babu (2008) as information and knowledge resources that are available in electronic forms including books, journals, journal articles, CDs, videos, databases, films audio digital products, online publishing, public domain and other intellectual properties that are available through internet. Digital information services have some benefits over the print information services as listed below:

- a) Multiple access is allowed
- b) Continuous access at any time and place
- c) Instant delivery
- d) Saving of shelf space
- e) Prevention from damage, loss or theft
- f) No shipping and handling
- g) Access to out of print materials

Digital information services are becoming dominant over the traditional information services nowadays and are mostly being offered by most of the libraries in India. As pointed out by Kaur (2009) and Kennedy (2011) that because of above unique characteristics mentioned for digital information services, the traditional marketing techniques may not be suitable for it. In the past, libraries have employed different marketing activities such as posters, bulletins, flyers/brochures, newsletter, user education and outreaches programs but with the emergence of digital information services the traditional marketing activities are not adequate. Therefore, digital marketing tools include library official website; e-communication like e-mail services, SMS ; and social networking tools like Facebook library page, library twitter account, library Whatsapp group, library LinkedIn account, wikis, library mobile app etc.

Nevertheless, the traditional marketing techniques like human interaction and promotional material would also complement the digital marketing techniques. Human interaction includes word of mouth, phone calls, office visit, and collaboration between faculty members, librarians and library users as marketing tools. Promotional material like posters, flyers/brochures, postcards/direct letters and newsletters could be employed where applicable.

1.2 SWOT ANALYSIS

SWOT is an acronym for Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats. SWOT analysis is a process of assessing the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of an information system and its environment. This scanning, gathering of customer relevant data and SWOT review helps the library to understand the best opportunity which are the products and services that meet the specified needs and desires of its customers.

SWOT analysis for a small corporate library (Hart, 1999) is given below:

Strengths

- (i) Good reputation with users
- (ii) Comprehensive collection of books, journals
- (iii) CD-ROMs and online databases
- (iv) Experienced and knowledge staff
- (v) Effective cataloguing and OPC system.

Weaknesses

- (i) Not well known to outside user base
- (ii) With just limited staff, cannot cope up with the busy times
- (iii) Inadequate infrastructures support for access
- (iv) Access problems with the locality, infrastructure.

Opportunities

- (i) Company intranet will reach most employees
- (ii) Management interested in knowledge management issues
- (iii) Company performance excellent and resources available for expansion.

Threats

- (i) Parent organisation management have appointed management consultancy to advice on knowledge management issues
- (ii) Some departments consider their own small collection to be adequate for their needs
- (iii) No natural successor to experienced librarian.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

YudaBakti and Sumaedi (2013) investigate the relationship between library customer loyalty and other latent constructs, namely service quality and customer satisfaction in a university library service in Indonesia. The research reveals that service quality has a direct effect on customer satisfaction, which then directly influences library customer loyalty. However, service quality does not have significant direct effect on customer loyalty in a library service. The library customer loyalty is not guaranteed if library management only improves the quality of the library services. Furthermore, to achieve library customer loyalty, library management has to assure the library customer satisfaction. Thus, since many factors can influence library customer satisfaction, library management should improve not only library service quality, but also other aspects that influence library customer satisfaction, such as perceived price, situational factor, and personal factor. Only a few empirical studies on customer loyalty were found in library service. More specifically, there is a lack of empirical

studies that investigated the relationship between library customer loyalty, service quality, and customer satisfaction. This paper has addressed this gap in the literature.

Anbu, Paul, and Mavuso (2012) finds that the library users can be successfully motivated and engaged to use the resources through SMS messaging and have the potential to market library services. It also finds out that there is a need to have a prototype for essential services for the benefit of the users as well as to market the library resources. This study presents a method for implementing SMS-based alert service in libraries. With the experience gained in a similar practical environment, an attempt has been made to create a prototype. This may serve as an important milestone in integrating such a service into the future integrated library services (ILS).

Gireesh (2013) discusses various social networking sites (SNS) such as Facebook, Twitter, Delicious, YouTube, Flickr etc. An outline of how the social media may successfully be applied to enhance the effectiveness in marketing library services and products is observed. Relative merits and challenges with adoption of SNS are also examined.

Gupta and Savard (2010) describe how marketing was applied to LIS over the years. Marketing is also related to other concepts used in the management of LIS. Finally the role of professional associations in diffusing marketing theory is portrayed and the importance of education addressed. The entry ends with a reflection on the future of marketing for LIS.

Islam and Hossain (2014) describe the marketing initiatives taken by university libraries to promote collection and services to their clientele. For this study, university library websites were examined using a checklist of criteria developed from earlier studies and present websites. The study identified that the websites are not fully utilized for marketing library resources and services, and the university libraries are not maximizing their promotional activities. A majority of libraries did not make any effort to provide online literacy courses, live support, copyright documents, and online user surveys, networking and so-on. The study is limited to Bangladeshi University libraries and generalization to others is to be cautioned, but there are important lessons to be learned. This paper will be helpful to libraries planning to implement a marketing strategic plan to improve outreach to users and enhance the image of the library.

It was found that there was very less or negligible amount of literature present in this area and there is huge gap in research field in Marketing and strategies applied to promote medical libraries' products and services in India and also at international level.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objectives of this study are:

- (i) To find out the marketing library services and products in digital environment
- (ii) To determine the promotional activities to market health libraries' services and products of studied libraries
- (iii) To examine the awareness and satisfaction level among the users about the products and services marketed by studied health libraries
- (iv) To conduct SWOT analysis of each studied health library

- (v) To prepare Customer profile and Market profile of each studied health library.

4. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The scope of the study is restricted to the two medical libraries in Delhi of National Medical Library (NML) and Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR) library. A random sampling was done to collect data from 30 users from each library in the year 2017.

5. METHODOLOGY AND ANALYSIS

A quantitative approach was used to identify the marketing and promotional activities of the libraries. A survey research involves acquiring information about their characteristics, opinions, attitudes, or previous experience - by asking questions and tabulating the answers. The questionnaire was designed keeping in view of the stated objectives. The structured questionnaire was mainly consisted of closed-ended and one open-ended question. Data was collected using a self-administered questionnaire and was processed and analyzed using GNU PSP software, which is an online clone software of IBM SPSS software and follow the same guiding principles and menus for statistics and data entry.

5.1 Market Profile

The market profile of the library was prepared on the basis of the response filled-in (see Annexure 1) by the head librarian or librarian-in-charge of the respective libraries. From the table 1, it can be observed that neither of the library have invested in the marketing of the library and have no promotion strategy or marketing strategy for their libraries.

Library	Marketing Fund	Designation person for marketing	Charged pattern	Promotional strategy	Own promotional resource
NLM	No	No	Free	No	No
ICMR Library	No	No	Free	No	No

Table 1: Market Profile of NLM and ICMR library

Furthermore, from table 2, it can be observed that NML is engaged with a single digital promotional activity i.e. having its own official library website and two non-digital promotional activities i.e. providing CAS service and displaying of new arrivals whereas ICMR have two digital promotional activities i.e. having an official library website and sending out e-mails to its users and three non-digital promotional activities services i.e. providing CAS service, preparing annual report and displaying of latest arrivals.

LIBRARY	PROMOTIONAL ACTIVITIES OFFERED
National Medical Library (NML)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Current Awareness Service • Display of new arrivals
Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • E-mail • Current Awareness Service • Annual Report • Display of latest arrivals

Table 2: Promotional activities offered by NML and ICMR library

5.2 Customer Profile

Customer Profile is a segmentation of the library users group so as to categorically group them for marketing and promotion purposes. Customer profiling may include demographical factor like age and gender of the customers; and / or Psychographics factor like preferences etc.

Table 3 is based on random sampling and analysis of data of questionnaire (see, Annexure 2) by GNU PSPP software filled-in by library users (where, N=30) of National Medical Library (NML) and Indian Medical Council of Research (ICMR) library. As it can be observed from the table, male customers are more in numbers in both the libraries than the female customers. Also, the age group of 20-30 years of customers is more dominant in both the libraries whereas in ICMR library there is still a wider range of age group customers but in less number. The usage of NML by customers is more on daily basis whereas ICMR library users ranges from daily to monthly. Most of the members at the NML are new users having membership of less than six months whereas at ICMR library, customer memberships is ranged from less than six months to 3 or more years.

CUSTOMER PROFILE			
National Medical Library (NML)		Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR)	
1. Gender	Male : 19 (63.33%) Female : 11 (36.67%)	1. Gender	Male : 21 (70%) Female : 9 (30%)
2. Age	20-30 age group : 25 (83.33%) 31-40 age group : 5 (16.67%)	2. Age	20-30 age group : 23 (76.67%) 31-40 age group : 5 (16.67%) 51-60 age group : 1 (3.33%) 60 and above age group : 1 (3.33%)
3. Usage	Daily : 27 (90%) Weekly : 3 (10%)	3. Usage	Daily : 12 (40%) Weekly : 6 (20%) Fortnightly : 5 (16.67%) Monthly : 6 (20%) Never : 1 (3.33%)
4. Membership	Less than six months: 17 (56.67%) Six months to a year : 7 (23.33%) 1-2 years : 4 (13.33%) 3 or more years : 2 (6.67%)	4. Membership	Less than six months: 8 (26.67%) Six months to a year : 6 (20%) 1-2 years : 10 (33.33%) 3 or more years : 6 (20%)

Table 3: Customer profile comparison of NML with ICMR library

5.3 SWOT Analysis

a) SWOT Analysis of National Medical Library (NML)

SWOT Analysis for National Medical Library (NML) was done using GNU PSPP software on the basis of the responses filled-in (see, Annexure 2) by the users of the library (where, N=30) who were selected randomly.

As it can be observed from the analysis of the data that the strength of the NML lies on its customer service experience; satisfaction of the library products and services by the users; on time responsiveness of the library staff to the users; reliability and usefulness of library products; having their own website and being recommended by most of the users to their friends or colleagues. The users have rated the library 4 out of a scale of 5 indicating the overall satisfaction and quality of library services and products being offered by the library.

On the other hand, the weaknesses of NML library lies at the poor use of social media and IT marketing tools to promote their products and services. Moreover, according to 87 users, the library does not conduct any orientation program to familiarize the users with the library resources and educating them how to use them which clearly indicates to the reason why the most of the users are not aware of the library products and services. In addition to this, the users who agreed to the fact the library staff is well trained and the librarian is a knowledgeable person is less than 50% which throw light on less interaction of the staff and librarian with the users.

There was a single open-ended question in the questionnaire which was designed for the opportunities section in the SWOT analysis. The Opportunities section helps the NML library

to work upon on the suggestions given by the users to provide better services and to emphasize on the demands of the users.

Lastly, there is a threat section which was based on the overall responses filled-in by the users. It was seen that almost all the users who filled-in the questionnaire were not aware of the services and products of the library which is a great threat to the utility of the resources of the library to its best.

i) Strength

1. Users have **rated the library 4 (Very Good)**, on a scale of 1 to 5
2. 53.33% (16) users rated 5 (Excellent) on a scale of 1 to 5 who would like to **recommend the library**
3. Users have rated **4 (Very Good)** on a scale of 1 to 5 on **customer service experience**
4. 60% (18) of the users are **satisfied** with the **library products and services**
5. According to 50% (15) users, **library is very responsive** to their queries
6. According to 60% (18) users, **library take about the same time** to response their queries
7. According to 70% (21) users, **library staff understands their queries very well**
8. According to 53.33% (16) users, library has their **own website**
9. According to 50% (15) and 56.67% (17) users, library **products are reliable and useful** respectively
10. According to 100% (30) users, **they use the library for education purpose**

ii) Weaknesses

1. According to about 90% (27) users, **library does not use Facebook, Twitter, Whatsapp, Blog, LinkedIN, Wikis, Library Mobile App and SMS marketing tools** to promote their products and services
2. According to 86.67% (26) users, **library does not conduct an orientation program** for the users
3. Majority of **the users does not know the products and services** offered by the library
4. According to 46.67% (14) users, **library staff is well trained** and carry the professional standard of conduct
5. According to 43.33% (13) users, **librarian is a professional** and knowledgeable person
6. According to 46.67% (14) users, **library is meeting their need** very well

iii) Opportunities

1. To have 24 hours user's access
2. To have Wi-Fi facility
3. To have more social media applications to interact and update the user with current library products and services

4. To acquire new editions of books present in the library and to revise with frequently
5. To acquire latest books related to health and medical sciences
6. To have library Mobile application
7. To have library communities and groups

iv) Threats

1. Unawareness of products and services offered by library

b) SWOT Analysis of Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR) Library

SWOT Analysis for Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR) library was undertaken using GNU PSPP software on the basis of the responses filled-in (see, Annexure 2) by the users of the library (where, N=30) who were selected randomly.

As observed by the analysis of the data filled-in by the users, it was found that the strength of ICMR library lies in its users' satisfaction with the products and services being offered by the library; meeting of users' needs by the library; understanding of users' queries by the library staff; usefulness of the library products to the users; well-trained library staff ; professional and knowledgeable librarian; users knowing some of the services and products of the library namely Circulation service and Journals, Newspapers as the products of the library. In addition to this, the users have rated 3 out of 5 to the overall satisfaction and quality of library's services and products.

On the other hand, the weaknesses of the ICMR library lies at its the poor use of social media and IT marketing tools to promote their products and services similar to that of NML. Moreover, according to 67% users, the library does not conduct any orientation program to familiarize the users with the library resources and educating them how to use them which indicates to the reason why the users are not aware to all the library products and services offered by the library and whether the library has its own website or not. Most of the users are not satisfied with the library staff's responsiveness to users' queries and the time taken to answer their queries. Moreover, very few users would like to recommend the library to their friends and colleagues.

There was a single open-ended question in the questionnaire which was designed for the opportunities section in the SWOT analysis. The Opportunities section helps the ICMR library to work upon on the suggestions given by the users to provide better services and to emphasize on the demands of the users.

Lastly, there is a threat section which was based on the overall responses filled-in by the users. It was seen that almost all the users who filled the questionnaire were not aware about all services and products of the library which is a great threat to the utility of the resources of the library to its best but knew some of the services and products unlike NML users.

i) Strength

1. Users have **rated the library 3 (Good)**, on a scale of 1 to 5
2. 60% (18) of **the users are satisfied** with the library products and services
3. According to 53.33% (16) users, **library staff is well trained** and carry the professional standard of conduct

4. According to 50% (15) users, **librarian is a professional** and knowledgeable person
5. According to 60% (18) users, **library is meeting their need** very well
6. According to 60% (18) users, **library staff understands their queries very well**
7. According to 73.33% (22) users, **library products is useful**
8. Around 60% of the **users know, uses and satisfied** with the **Circulation service ; Journals and Newspaper products** in the library

ii) Weaknesses

1. 33.33% (10) users would like to **recommend the library**
2. According to 43.33% (13) users, **library is very responsive** to their queries
3. According to 46.67% (14) users, library has their **own website**
4. According to 46.67% (14) users, **library take about the same time** to response their queries
5. According to about 90% (27) users, **library does not use Facebook, Twitter, Whatsapp, Blog, LinkedIN, Wikis, Library Mobile App and SMS marketing tools** to promote their products and services
6. According to 66.67% (20) users, **library does not conduct an orientation program** for the users

iii) Opportunities

1. To acquire more books and develop their library collection
2. To subscribe to special software like Plagiarism tools
3. To acquire more online subscribed journals
4. To have more social media application services to interact and update the user with current library products and services
5. To increase the number of books issued by a user
6. To digitize library resources
7. To send articles by e-mail or post

iv) Threats

1. Unawareness of the products and services offered by the library

6. CONCLUSION

Digital marketing tools are the need of the hour and should be implemented in all the libraries, especially the medical libraries for users' communication, exchange of information and proper utilization of resources who are highly engaged in research. Information literacy programs and orientation program should be frequently arranged to literate the users as to how to use a medical library and its resources which would directly reflect on the maximum use of the expensive resources of the medical libraries. As the government provide a huge

amount of funding to medical libraries for the acquisition of medical library resources, negligence towards the marketing of these resources will do injustice to the money invested. The incompetency of the library to market the library services and products hinders a qualitative research and hence, the growth and development of a nation.

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ANNEXURE 1

Survey about the information products and services marketed in a medical library environment

Librarian of

Mark only one oval

1. Does your library have the provision of providing fund for marketing its information products and services?

Yes

No

2.If yes, what proportion of the library budget is designated for the activities related with marketing?

Less than 1%

1-5%

6-10%

More than 10%

3. Do you undertake any marketing and promotional activities to promote your service in the following areas?

	Yes	No
Newsletters (paper and electronic)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Websites	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Email	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Training and events	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Outreach	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Current Awareness	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Knowledge Management services	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Annual Report	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Display latest arrivals	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Pamphlets/Brochures/Leaflets	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Blog	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Wiki	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Facebook	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Twitter	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Library Mobile Application	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
SMS Service	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Workshops	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

4. Does your library have a specially designated person for marketing?

Yes

No

5. Do you charge your users for using library information products and services?

Yes

No

6. The charging pattern of your library is

Free

Cost recovery method

Nominal cost method

Cost plus pricing method

Other: _____

7. Do you have a marketing/promotional strategy or equivalent (formal or otherwise)?

Yes

No

Other: _____

8. Have you created your own promotional resources?

Yes

No

Other: _____

9. Which are the following services provided by your library?

	Free	Charged
Circulation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Inter Library Loan	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reference Service	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Current Awareness Service	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Selective Dissemination of Information	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Indexing Service	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Abstracting Service	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Bibliographic Service	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Patents information	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Online/CD-ROM Search	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Newspaper Clipping Service	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reprographic Service	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Translational Service	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Table of Content	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Standards Information	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Literature Search	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

10. Which are the products provided by your library?

	Journals	Abstracting/Indexing	Bulletin	Newsletters	Press Clipping	Bibliographical List	Documentation List	Online/CD-ROM Database
Free	<input type="radio"/>							
Charged	<input type="radio"/>							